

J TANTA MEDICAL JOURNAL

ISSN 1110-1415

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Reprint

From

**Tanta Medical Journal
Vol. 27, No. 1, June 30, 1999**

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ABSTRACT

Fungal keratitis is a severe ocular infection secondary to accidental macro or microscopic trauma of the cornea. Dramatic increase of this infection was recorded along with the spread of antibiotic and heavy corticosteroids. This fungal disease is difficult to treat because of the scarcity of efficacious topical and systemic drugs. We evaluated in vivo and in vitro effectiveness of Povidone Iodine (PVP-I [betadine]), an agent with broad antibacterial and antiviral activity on *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger* isolates from patients with fungal keratitis. The results showed that PVP-I solution 5% - 10% has a in vivo fungicidal activity against the vegetative cells of *Candida albicans* but not spores of *Aspergillus niger*.

INTRODUCTION

Although corneal infection have worldwide distribution, the incidence of fungal infections is higher in tropical and semitropical areas¹:

The severity of the disease is due to misdiagnosis as H.S keratitis or to the scarcity of effective topical and systemic drugs. Nevertheless, the

study of chemotherapeutic agents with low toxicity and high fungicidal activity is required ⁽²⁾.

Prophylactic measures are taken prior to surgery as a means to eliminate pathogens from the surgical field and surgical staff, that may become a cause of infection in the unhealed wound. Various antiseptics are available in the market for the purpose of sterilizing tissues and surgical instruments. Povidone Iodine is (PVP-I) one of the most commonly used solutions that has proven its efficacy over the years of use since being introduced in the market ⁽³⁾.

Various specific antifungal agents have been used polyenes, amphotricin 0.15% with varying degree of success. However, these specific antifungal agents are not usually available in developing countries and are expensive. Even in U.K. They are not available commercially for use in the eye but only in designated referral centers ⁽⁴⁾.

PVP-I is an antiseptic agent that is used as a topical ocular antimicrobial agent appears promising, particularly in developing countries, although studies are required to determine its efficacy in treating different ocular infections and to identify any side effects associated with frequent use ⁽⁵⁾.

PVP-I. was recently used as a prophylaxis against neonatal conjunctivitis in prospective trials, instead of treatment with silver nitrate or erythromycin because of it's lower toxicity and lower cost ⁽⁶⁾.

AIM OF THE WORK

Aim of this work is to investigate and evaluate the efficacy of both in vivo and in vitro effectiveness of Povidone-Iodine as an agent with broad antibacterial and antiviral activity on fungus isolates from patients with fungal keratitis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

I- Fungi isolates :

Tested fungi were isolated from patients with severely fungal keratitis clinically diagnosed as fungal keratitis according to Magro et al. ⁽⁷⁾, purified and identified, then stock suspensions of vegetative cells from *Candida albicans* as a yeast fungi and spores of *Aspergillus niger* as a filamentous fungus were prepared in sterile distilled water in concentration of 56×10^4 CFU/ml for *Candida albicans*, and 62×10^4 CFU /ml for *Aspergillus niger*. Fungi were isolated from patients before treatment initiation so the different sensitivities shown by the isolates were not related to previously acquired drug resistance.

Candida albicans and *Aspergillus niger* are the most common isolates although a wide range of other genera are found ⁽⁴⁾.

Czapek's-dox agar (for *A. niger*) and sabouraud's dextrose agar (for *C. albicans*) were prepared and autoclaved. (Nassar Pharmchemical Industry Co.).

Fungal suspensions (0.5 ml) were mixed with the corresponding media (10 ml) in each sterile Petri plate at 50 °C, homogenized then let to solidify at room temperature and incubated at 35 °C for 24 hours for *C. albicans* and 72 hours for *A. niger*.

II- Pharmaceutical agents :

Aqueous polyvinyl pyrolidone and Iodine [Betadine] (PVP-I) is available as a 5 percent or 10 percent solution, and can be then diluted to the needed concentration. It was prepared in distilled water under sterile conditions and stored at room temperature in opaque containers and used within one hour as the instruction by the manufacture. (Nile Pharma. Cairo. ARE under license by Mandi, Pharma AG Basel , Switzerland).

The sensitivities of isolates to the following 2.5%, 5% and 10% pharmaceutical concentration were determined.

III- Experimental design

(A) Fungicidal effects of PVP-I in vitro :

According to the method of Magro ⁽⁷⁾, sterile 4.0 mm paper disc (Whatman international Ltd. Maidston .U.K) were soaked in 2.5% , 5% or 10% PVP-I solution till saturation, placed on the previous plates with fungal isolates suspension and cultured for 24 hours for *Candida albicans* and 72 hours for *Asperigallus niger* at 35°C. After the incubation period the fungicidal effect of each solution was determined by observing for any fungal growth on the paper discs or around using the inverted microscope to detect the inhibitory zone. The experiment was repeated twice and the mean of the inhibitory zone was taken.

Unfortunately, there is no universally recognized fungus with known susceptibilities that could be used as a control.

(B) Fungicidal effects of PVP-I in vivo :

Sixteen Albino rabbit twins of both sexes were adapted to lab condition for 3 days according to the ARVO statement for use of animals in ophthalmology and vision research. 5% concentration of PVP-1 was applied to the right eye of each rabbit and 10% concentration of PVP-I was applied to the left eye. 2.5% concentration was excluded from in vivo experiment because its ineffective fungicidal activity in vitro.

Tear film was collected from the conjunctival sac after the desired periods by sterile filter paper 4.0 mm disc diameter. After scarification of the rabbits aqueous (2 ml) was aspirated from anterior chamber using 27 gauge needle syringe and put on the plates with fungal isolates suspension ⁽⁸⁾.

The conjunctival, central corneal and peripheral corneal discs (4.0 mm trephine) were taken. Tear film, aqueous, conjunctival and corneal discs were put on cultured plates with isolates of fungi previously prepared as in vitro testing under aseptic conditions and the plates were incubated at 35°C and recording of the diameter of inhibition zone in centimeter after 24 hours for *C. albicans* and 72 hours for *A. niger* using a leitz inverted microscope. Scarification was done after half hour, one hour, 2 hours and 6 hours. Four eyes for each time of scarification were done and the mean of the inhibitory zones was taken.

We classified the in vivo test into two groups :-

Group (A) Intact cornea :

PVP-I 5% or 10% was applied to an intact cornea .

Group (B) Denuded cornea :

PVP-I was applied to the cornea after making epithelial defect 4.0 mm paper disc (Whatman inter-national Ltd. Maidstone U.K) immersed in 30% alcohol was applied to the cornea for 10 seconds after rabbits were anesthetized topically with Benoxinate hydrochloride 0.4% .

The paper discs were then removed, creating a reproducible circular defect in the corneal epithelium. (The epithelial defects were made in animals since fungi cannot infect cornea with intact epithelium), then the corneal surface was washed with 40 ml of sterile saline.

Negative control of untreated rabbit's eye was tested and put on the cultured plates with fungal isolates suspension.

RESULTS

Fungicidal effect of PVP-I in vitro :

Table (1) and figure (I) reported in vitro drug activities on the yeast and filamentous forms of fungi. Lower concentration 5% PVP-I showed mean inhibitory zone diameter of 0.62 cm for *C. albicans* and a mean 0.43 cm for *A. niger* while the higher concentration 10% PVP-I showed mean inhibitory zone 0.82 cm for *C. albicans* and a mean 0.68 cm for *A. niger*. Lower 2.5% concentration showed no effect on both isolates, photo I (B & D).

Fungicidal effect of PVP-I in vivo :

Group "A" Intact cornea.

From table II figure II, Half an hour after application tissue treated with PVP-I 5% showed mean inhibitory zone 0.45 cm for the conjunctiva, a mean 0.64 cm for central cornea, peripheral cornea and tear film for the treated *C. albicans* but showed larger mean inhibitory zone for 10% concentration treated eye tissues. While *Aspiregillus niger* showed no inhibitory zone, (Photo II).

One hour after application of 5% concentration smaller inhibitory zone was noticed as regard the tear film, conjunctiva and both central and peripheral cornea but still larger inhibitory zone for 10% concentration for *C. albicans*. No inhibitory zone was detected in *Aspiregillus niger* isolates, (Photo II).

After two hours, no inhibitory zone was noticed even in *Candida albicans* species.

Group (B) Denuded cornea :

From table III and figure III, Half an hour after application tissue treated with PVP-I 5% showed an inhibitory zone with a mean 0.44 cm for the conjunctiva and a mean 0.52 cm for central, peripheral denuded

cornea and tear film for treated *Candida albicans* suspension isolates and showed larger inhibitory zone for 10% concentration. One hour after application a mean inhibitory zone smaller than half an hour as regard the tear film, conjunctiva and both central and peripheral cornea but still larger zone in 10% concentration. Two hours no inhibitory zone was detected for *C. albicans*. No inhibitory zone was detected in *A. niger* isolates suspension, (Photo I).

Table IV showed no inhibitory zone in different eye tissues of untreated rabbit eye on both *C. albicans* and *A. niger*.

Table (I) : Showing the mean inhibitory zone in cm. with different concentration of Povidone iodine on *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger* (positive control).

PVP-I Conc.	5%	10%
<i>C. albicans</i> .	0.62	0.82
<i>A. niger</i> .	0.43	0.68

Table (II) : Showing the mean inhibitory zone in cm. with different concentration of Povidone iodine in different eye tissues on *Candida albicans* in intact cornea group .

Time	Half hour Loading					One hour Loading				
	C.C.	P.C.	Aq.	Conj.	T.F.	C.C.	P.C.	Aq.	Conj	T.F.
5%	0.64	0.65	0	0.45	0.60	0.32	0.51	0	0.43	0.54
10%	0.82	0.81	0	0.83	0.85	0.42	0.61	0	0.63	0.52

Table (II) Cont.

Time	Two hours Loading					six hours Loading				
	C.C.	P.C.	Aq.	Conj.	T.F.	C.C.	P.C.	Aq.	Conj	T.F.
5%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

N.B. 0 means no inhibitory zone was detected and the fungi grow on the discs. C.C.= central cornea, P.C.= peripheral cornea, Conj = conjunctiva, T.F.= tear film.

Table (III) : Showing the mean inhibitory zone in cm. with different concentration of Povidone iodine in different eye tissues on *Candida albicans* in denuded cornea group.

Time	Half hour Loading					One hour Loading					
	Eye tissue	C.C.	P.C.	Aq.	Conj.	T.F.	C.C.	P.C.	Aq.	Conj.	T.F.
5%		0.52	0.52	0	0.44	0.52	0.31	0.42	0	0.40	0.53
10%		0.71	0.72	0	0.63	0.64	0.42	0.51	0	0.65	0.63

Table (III) Cont.

Time	Two hours Loading					six hours Loading					
	Eye tissue	C.C.	P.C.	Aq.	Conj.	T.F.	C.C.	P.C.	Aq.	Conj.	T.F.
5%		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10%		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table (IV) : Showing the inhibitory zone of untreated rabbit's eye (Negative control).

Eye tissue	Central cornea (C.C.)	Peripheral cornea (P.C.)	Aqueous (Aq.)	Tear film (T.F.)	Conjunctiva (Conj.)
<i>C. albicans</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>A. niger.</i>	0	0	0	0	0

Fig. (I) : Showing the mean inhibitory zone in cm with different concentration of Povidone iodine on *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*.

Fig. (II) : Showing the mean inhibitory zone in cm with different concentration of Povidone iodine in different eye tissues on Candida albicans in intact cornea.

Fig. (III) : Showing the mean inhibitory zone in cm with different concentration of Povidone iodine in different eye tissues on Candida albicans in denuded cornea.

Photo I

Inhibition zones of 5% & 10 % P.I. after 30min. & 1 h. in conjunctiva on Candiada plates.

Inhibition zones of 5% & 10 % P.I. after 30min. & 1 h. in peripheral cornea on Candiada plates.

Inhibition zones of 5% & 10 % P.I. after 30min. & 1 h. in tear film on Candiada plates.

Inhibition zones of 5% & 10 % P.I. after 30min. & 1 h. in central cornea on Candiada plates.

Inhibition zones of 5% & 10 % P.I. after 30min. & 1 h. in aquous on Candiada plates.

Photo II

DISCUSSION

Over years various therapeutic agents regimens have been proposed, but non has shown constant effectiveness in achieving a clinical and fungicidal cure.

Our objective was to set up a simple method of testing fungi against an antiseptic agent to give abroad indication of its potential efficacy.

Our method is cheep, easily reproducible and requires only very basic materials and technical skills.

In agreement with Rahman (1998) ⁽⁹⁾, we believe that the effectiveness of an antifungal agent on fungi is of clinical value when it causes the complete destruction of both vegetable cells and spore form.

We evaluated the efficacy of two concentration of PVP -I on various fungal isolates from patients with proven cases of fungal keratitis in vivo and in vitro.

Martin et al (1995) ⁽⁴⁾ mentioned that Povidone iodine showed a good response at all concentrations in vitro , this agree with our results in vitro for 5% and 10% concentration but not 2.5%.

However Martin and Johnson et al ⁽⁴⁾, mentioned that in a small pilot study conducted in India to assess clinical efficacy for fungal corneal ulcers, Povidone iodine was ineffective.

Povidone iodine has been shown to be effective against *Aspergillus niger* introduced into rabbit eye ⁽¹⁰⁾ .

Our results showed that PVP-I was effective in vivo against strains of Candidiasis but the filamentous group showed resistant may be due to spores formation. Pierard et al. ⁽¹¹⁾ mentioned that regular applications of PVP-I for two weeks significantly abated the fungal invasiveness inside human stratum corneum.

In conclusion :

Our study emphasizes the importance of cultivating fungal strains and species causing keratitis in vitro and the importance of performing a drug sensitivity assay on the isolate at the beginning of therapy or at later stage.

Our method is cheap, easily reproducible and requires only very basic materials and technical skills.

Our results show that normal eye secretion have no antifungal activity.

In particular, our results demonstrate that PVP-I show in vivo better antifungal activity on only yeast but not filamentous forms due to more resistant spores.

Our results show that PVP-I is more effective in higher concentration which may be toxic to the cornea.

Our results show that PVP-I is not penetrative and so it can be used only in superficial infection and denudation of the cornea have no effect on the penetrative property. PVP-I persist for one hour in the cornea and so it is recommended as preoperative topical disinfectant against candidiasis and in postoperative periods or in suppurative fungal keratitis with one hour frequency.

Also, our results need to be confirmed with other fungus strains and species in association with other drugs in vitro and in experimental animal models.

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